

1 **Exploring climate change exposure of the Mediterranean Sea through 3D climate velocity**

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8

9 **ABSTRACT**

10 Climate change is increasingly challenging the durability of marine conservation and spatial planning
11 approaches that rely on contemporary climate baselines. In response, the identification and protection
12 of climate refugia – areas expected to remain relatively stable under climate change – has emerged
13 as a key strategy for climate-smart conservation. However, in marine systems, refugia are commonly
14 delineated using surface conditions alone, overlooking the vertical structure of the ocean. Here, we
15 assess climate change exposure across the entire Mediterranean Sea water column using an analogue-
16 based climate velocity framework in three-dimensional space. We compared present (2006-2030) and
17 near-future (2031-2055) temperature conditions using nine climate variables, constraining the search
18 for climatic analogues within ecologically meaningful depth ranges. Projected temperature conditions
19 shifted in three dimensions across most of the basin: 45.8% of the Mediterranean exhibited combined
20 horizontal and vertical displacement of climate conditions, while an additional 13.4% showed
21 predominantly vertical shifts, indicating that climate change does not operate solely through
22 horizontal redistribution. The basin-wide mean three-dimensional climate velocity was 2.98 km yr⁻¹,

23 with pronounced depth- and region-specific differences. Climate exposure was highest in the euphotic
24 zone and in deep regions such as the Ionian Sea, whereas deeper biozones of the Western
25 Mediterranean appeared comparatively more stable than those of the Eastern region. By integrating
26 depth-resolved climate data within a fully three-dimensional framework, this study provides the first
27 basin-scale assessment of climate velocity across the Mediterranean water column and offers a robust
28 foundation for climate-smart conservation and planning.

29

30 **KEYWORDS**

31 Climate velocity; climate analogues; vertical climate change; marine climate refugia; Mediterranean
32 Sea; marine spatial planning

33 1. INTRODUCTION

34 Climate change is profoundly altering marine ecosystems by driving shifts in species distributions
35 and modifying patterns of species occurrence (Pinsky et al., 2020, 2025). These changes disrupt
36 community dynamics, reshape ecosystem structure, and affect ecosystem functioning and the services
37 they provide (Doney et al., 2012; Pecl et al., 2017). Such impacts are expected to reduce the
38 effectiveness of current conservation strategies, such as marine protected areas (MPAs), as only a
39 subset may be able to maintain the biodiversity they currently support (Dobrowski et al., 2021;
40 Kyprioti et al., 2021). In parallel, the redistribution of human activities in response to climate change
41 may intensify spatial conflicts, underscoring the need for adaptive maritime spatial planning (MSP).
42 Consequently, projected climate-driven changes are expected to impact ecosystem functioning,
43 biodiversity, and human uses, challenging existing conservation and management frameworks and
44 underscoring the need for climate-smart conservation – and particularly climate-smart MSP – to
45 ensure that conservation objectives remain effective under future climate scenarios (Frazão Santos et
46 al., 2020, 2024; Gissi et al., 2019; Solidoro et al., 2022).

47 To operationalise climate-smart conservation and MSP, particular emphasis has been placed on
48 identifying and protecting climate refugia, which are increasingly seen as key targets for conservation
49 (Brito-Morales et al., 2022; Buenafe et al., 2023; Doxa, Kamarianakis, et al., 2022). These areas
50 buffer species, populations, or ecosystems from climate change by maintaining relatively stable
51 environmental conditions over time, allowing resident biodiversity to persist in place (Carroll et al.,
52 2017; Keppel et al., 2012; Loarie et al., 2009). Such refugia are often characterised by high
53 environmental heterogeneity, offering a variety of microhabitats that facilitate persistence,
54 movement, or adaptation. Historically, they have supported species survival during past climate
55 fluctuations and are considered critical for maintaining ecological stability under ongoing and future
56 climate change (Brown et al., 2022; Michalak et al., 2020).

57 Several approaches have been proposed to identify potential refugia. These include estimating the
58 ratio between temporal climate trends and spatial climate gradients within a surrounding
59 neighbourhood (Burrows et al., 2014; Loarie et al., 2009); calculating the distance to future locations
60 with similar climate conditions (Hamann et al., 2015; Kyprioti et al., 2021; Ordonez & Williams,
61 2013); assessing changes in habitat suitability (Serra-Diaz et al., 2014); and mapping where suitable
62 conditions for species are projected to persist in the future (Carroll et al., 2015). Together, these
63 methods highlight different dimensions of how refugia can support the persistence of biodiversity
64 under climate change.

65 Among these approaches, analogue-based climate velocity enables an analysis centred on exposure
66 to change, identifying refugia in areas less exposed to climatic stressors and that maintain stable
67 climatic conditions between the present and the future (Kyprioti et al., 2021). This method estimates
68 the distance an organism would need to cover to reach future locations with climatic conditions
69 similar to those of its current habitat, effectively tracking the displacement of climatic niches over
70 time (Kyprioti et al., 2021; Queirós et al., 2021). Locations with nearby future climate analogues, or
71 where conditions remain stable, are potential refugia, while those with only distant or no analogues
72 at all are seen as climate change hotspots. While originally developed in terrestrial systems (Carroll
73 et al., 2017; Haight & Hammill, 2020; Loarie et al., 2009), this method is increasingly applied in the
74 marine realm to assess climate stability within conservation areas (e.g., Brito-Morales et al., 2022;
75 Doxa, Almpanidou, et al., 2022; Kyprioti et al., 2021). It also enables the identification of disturbance
76 refugia – areas where key physical, ecological, and sociocultural features may persist under climate
77 stress (Morelli et al., 2016; Saunders et al., 2023).

78 To date, most marine applications of climate velocity have computed climate analogues on sea surface
79 temperature (SST), due to its ecological relevance, strong link with other biogeochemical variables,
80 and the availability of high-resolution datasets from satellite and in situ observations (Brito-Morales
81 et al., 2018; Sanz-Martín et al., 2024). However, many marine species, including plankton, demersal

82 fish, and benthic invertebrates, respond to temperature shifts across depth as well as horizontally
83 (Dulvy et al., 2008; Poloczanska et al., 2016; Von Schuckmann et al., 2023). In such cases, suitable
84 thermal conditions may be tracked through relatively small vertical shifts, rather than the large
85 horizontal displacements typically implied by climate velocity estimates derived from horizontal
86 gradients alone (Gruenburg et al., 2025). Importantly, warming is not confined to the upper layer of
87 the ocean. Although the 0-700 m layer absorbs most of the excess heat, measurable warming also
88 occurs at intermediate depths (700-2000 m) and even in deep and abyssal waters, where these depths
89 can contribute roughly 10-15% of the global ocean heat-content increase (Cheng et al., 2016;
90 Desbruyères et al., 2016; Von Schuckmann et al., 2023). Relying solely on SST may be adequate for
91 organisms inhabiting the euphotic zone, but it provides an incomplete and potentially misleading
92 representation of climate change for species living at depth, where the rate and direction of change
93 can differ substantially (Brito-Morales et al., 2018). This potential limitation arises because SST can
94 fail to capture subsurface thermal dynamics and vertical heterogeneity (Radin & Nieves, 2024; Zhang
95 et al., 2023), which are ecologically fundamental features of three-dimensional marine environments.
96 Some recent studies have incorporated depth by calculating horizontal velocity within stratified depth
97 zones (e.g., Brito-Morales et al., 2020; Doxa, Almpnidou, et al., 2022), but these often assume
98 homogeneity within depth layers, overlooking the combination of horizontal and vertical structures
99 of climate velocity.

100 In this study, we explore climate refugia across the vertical domain by computing three-dimensional
101 analogue-based climate velocity – across latitude and longitude, depth, and time – throughout the
102 Mediterranean Sea. This basin is a recognised global climate change hotspot due to its semi-enclosed
103 nature, steep environmental gradients, and accelerated warming trends (Adloff et al., 2015; Giorgi,
104 2006; Vargas-Yáñez et al., 2008). Climate impacts are spatially heterogeneous across the
105 Mediterranean, reflecting differences in circulation patterns, bathymetry, and thermal structure
106 among sub-regions (Bethoux & Gentili, 1996; Reale et al., 2022). This is the first study to apply a

107 fully 3D analogue-based climate velocity to the Mediterranean basin, providing a spatially explicit
108 framework for integrating vertical and horizontal climate refugia into climate-smart ocean planning.

109

110 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

111 *2.1 Defining the 3D analogue-based climate velocity*

112 Analogue-based climate velocity quantifies the distance to the closest location whose future climate
113 is analogous to a location's current climate (Ordonez & Williams, 2013), divided by the time interval
114 over which the change is evaluated. The original climate velocity metric proposed by Loarie et al.
115 (2009) relied on local spatial gradients, expressing velocity as the ratio between the temporal rate of
116 change in a climate variable (e.g., temperature) and its spatial gradient in the area surrounding the
117 focal location. In contrast, analogue-based approaches expand the search beyond local gradients,
118 identifying climatically similar locations across the entire study region (Brito-Morales et al., 2018;
119 Carroll et al., 2015; Ordonez & Williams, 2013).

120 In this study, we further advance analogue-based climate velocity by extending the search for climate
121 analogues into the vertical dimension (Figure 1). We calculated geographic distances in a projected
122 metric space (X, Y) combined with depth (Z), enabling the detection of climate analogues both
123 horizontally and vertically. This 3D implementation provides a more realistic representation of how
124 species and habitats may track suitable conditions throughout the water column.

125

126 **[Figure 1 here]**

127

128 *2.2 Climate data*

129 We applied the 3D analogue-based method to calculate forward climate velocity to a depth-resolved
130 temperature dataset covering the entire water column of the Mediterranean Sea. We used daily sea
131 temperature data from 2006 to 2055, simulated by the POLCOMS-ERSEM coupled model system
132 under the Representative Conservation Pathway (RCP) 8.5 scenario, available in the Copernicus
133 Climate Data Store (C3S, CDS, 2020; Kay et al., 2020). The dataset has a horizontal resolution of
134 $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (approximately 11 km) and includes 43 irregularly spaced vertical layers ranging from
135 0.5 m to 5500 m in depth (Table S1). The RCP 8.5 scenario represents the highest-emission pathway,
136 with radiative forcing peaking at 8.5 W m^{-2} ($\sim 940 \text{ ppm CO}_2$) and projecting a median increase in
137 near-surface sea temperature of $5\text{-}6^\circ\text{C}$ by 2100 (NOAA, 2013; Riahi et al., 2011; Sillmann et al.,
138 2013). Originally conceived as a high-end, worst-case scenario, we adopt it here as a plausible
139 “business-as-usual” pathway, as recent studies suggest it closely tracks observed emissions during
140 the early decades of the century (Schwalm et al., 2020).

141 The dataset’s time series was divided into two 25-year periods, representing contemporary (2006-
142 2030) and near-future (2031-2055) conditions. For each period, we computed nine temperature-based
143 bioclimatic variables (O’Donnell & Ignizio, 2012) and averaged them over the 25-year period for
144 each cell across all depth layers. Variables included annual mean temperature, diurnal range,
145 isothermality, temperature seasonality, maximum and minimum temperature, annual range, and mean
146 temperature of the warmest and coldest quarters (Table S2). These variables are widely used to
147 investigate species distributions under both current and future climatic conditions (de Jesus Almeida
148 et al., 2025). We selected them because they capture annual and seasonal trends, as well as extreme
149 or limiting environmental factors. Collectively, they provide a basis for identifying shifts in climate
150 types and the potential emergence of novel climate patterns (Bazzato et al., 2021; Bede-Fazekas &
151 Somodi, 2024). These bioclimatic variables define the multivariate climate space used to identify
152 climatic analogues between contemporary and future conditions. All data processing was conducted

153 in Python (version 3.9.18). The complete computational workflow is implemented in a publicly
154 available code repository (Rizzi et al., 2026).

155 To reduce dimensionality, avoid collinearity among predictors, and ensure comparability across
156 variables with different units, we performed a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on the combined
157 present and future bioclimatic datasets encompassing the full 3D water column. Before the PCA,
158 bioclimatic variables were standardised by centring to zero mean and scaling to unit variance. We
159 subsequently examined how the structure of bioclimatic variability and the contribution of individual
160 variables to the retained principal components varied with depth (Figure S1-S3). To this end, we
161 evaluated PCA loadings and bioclimatic patterns for the entire vertical domain of analysis and within
162 four ecologically meaningful vertical biozones: 0-40 m (euphotic), 40-200 m (mesophotic), 200-1000
163 m (mesopelagic), and >1000 m (bathabyssopelagic). These were built on the three-zone division
164 (surface, mesopelagic, and bathabyssopelagic) described by Rogers (2015), and we further split the
165 surface layer into euphotic and mesophotic zones, following the classification by Doxa, Almpanidou,
166 et al. (2022) (Table S2). This analysis revealed pronounced vertical differences in thermal structure
167 across the Mediterranean. Temperature-related variables exhibited strong gradients and higher
168 variability in the upper layers, whereas the deeper layers were comparatively stable (Figures S1-S2).
169 Moreover, the contribution of individual bioclimatic variables to the retained principal components
170 varied among biozones (Figure S3), indicating depth-dependent climatic structure. These consistent
171 vertical differences in both projected change and variable relationships support stratifying the
172 analogue-based climate velocity analysis into four depth zones. Consequently, we retained the first
173 three principal components, which together explained over 95% of the total variance in each depth
174 range (Figure S1), for subsequent analyses.

175

176 *2.3 3D Climate velocity computation*

177 We calculated 3D climate velocity independently within each vertical biozone using an analogue-
178 based approach (Carroll et al., 2015; Kyprioti et al., 2021; Ordonez & Williams, 2013). Climate
179 distances were measured as Euclidean distance in PCA space derived from the multivariate climate
180 dataset. To determine which locations could serve as valid climatic analogues, we applied a similarity
181 threshold to the resulting climate distance matrix. In contrast to previous analogue-based climate
182 velocity implementations, which either rely on biome-derived distance cut-offs (Ordonez &
183 Williams, 2013) or on discretisation of multivariate climate space into predefined bins (Carroll et al.,
184 2015; Kyprioti et al., 2021), we developed a continuous, distance-based similarity framework
185 calibrated through sensitivity analysis. By systematically varying the similarity threshold, we jointly
186 evaluated analogue displacement distances and the proportion of areas with no future climate
187 analogue. We derived a biozone-specific threshold that maximised the interpretability of 3D climate
188 velocity while preserving spatial continuity (Figure S4). This approach explicitly addresses the trade-
189 off inherent to analogue-based methods between overly permissive thresholds that allow distance and
190 potentially implausible analogue matches and overly restrictive thresholds that inflate the prevalence
191 of no analogue conditions (Hamann et al., 2015). It also avoids ecological assumptions implicit in
192 biome-based thresholds and discretisation artefacts. All locations whose climate distance from a focal
193 cell fell within this threshold were retained as candidate future analogues.

194 Because each biozone represents a distinct thermal environment, the analogue search was constrained
195 to the same vertical range as the focal cell. To allow limited vertical connectivity while still preserving
196 biozone-specific thermal structure, we incorporated a vertical buffer comprising one depth layer
197 above and one below the boundaries of each biozone. Potential analogues were therefore searched
198 only within the biozone and the adjacent layer.

199 For each cell, all eligible locations that met the climate similarity threshold were evaluated
200 geographically. Following Ordonez & Williams (2013) and Carroll et al. (2015), the climate analogue
201 was defined as the geographically nearest location within the analogue set. To determine this, we

202 computed the Euclidean distance in the projected metric space (X, Y, Z) between the focal cell and
203 all candidate analogue cells within the same depth range. The nearest location (i.e., the minimum
204 distance match) was selected as the climate analogue.

205 Forward climate velocity was calculated by dividing the geographic distance to the selected future
206 analogue by the 25-year interval between present and future conditions, yielding a 3D velocity vector
207 in the water-column space. All steps of the analogue-based climate velocity computation were
208 implemented in Python and are fully reproducible using the code archived on Zenodo (Rizzi et al.,
209 2026).

210

211 *2.3 Vertical and spatial analysis to identify refugia and hotspots*

212 The 3D climate velocity vector was subsequently partitioned into horizontal (V_{xy}) and vertical (V_z)
213 components to facilitate interpretation. The horizontal component represents the vector distance of
214 analogues in East-North space and quantifies the magnitude of horizontal displacement. The vertical
215 component is calculated as the difference in depth between the initial and analogue locations, with
216 positive values indicating upward shifts and negative values indicating downward shifts. To describe
217 the direction of horizontal movement, we also computed the angle of the V_{xy} vector relative to the x-
218 axis (East) and subsequently converted it to a compass bearing, measured clockwise from North, with
219 poleward movement corresponding to 0° and equatorward to 180° .

220 We then explored depth-related patterns of climate velocity and identify potential climate refugia.
221 For each biozone, climate velocity was summarised using the mean, interquartile range (IQR), and
222 maximum velocity (Max). Moreover, cells lacking a future analogue within the climate distance
223 threshold were classified as “no analogue”, while cells with zero horizontal and vertical displacement
224 were classified as “no change”, representing locations predicted to remain stable.

225 To depict differences in patterns of climate exposure across the Mediterranean, we analysed the
226 results over different geographical domains: (i) the entire Mediterranean basin, and (ii) individual
227 basins. Basins were defined following the regional subdivision of Manca et al. (2004), which reflects
228 major oceanographic and circulation features of the Mediterranean (Figure S5; Table S3).

229 To further investigate depth dependence, we calculated a normalised Euclidean dissimilarity index
230 (Legendre & Legendre, 2012) for both the horizontal (V_{xy}) and vertical (V_z) components of climate
231 velocity across depth layers. This index quantifies the dissimilarity between full 2D grids at two
232 depths, computed as a range-normalised Euclidean distance and aggregated across the horizontal grid
233 for each depth, with higher values indicating greater dissimilarity.

234 Finally, we examined the 3D climate velocity vectors at the Mediterranean Sea surface (0.5 m),
235 considering both their horizontal and vertical components. Separately, we also calculated a forward
236 velocity constrained to the seafloor by limiting the search for analogues to bottom grid cells; in this
237 case, analogue coordinates were extracted in three dimensions (X, Y, Z), but velocity was computed
238 solely from horizontal (X-Y) distances, without considering vertical displacement.

239

240 **3. RESULTS**

241 *3.1 Horizontal component of climate velocity*

242 Under the extreme climate emissions scenario (RCP 8.5), the Mediterranean Sea was projected to
243 experience substantial shifts in environmental conditions throughout the water column. The mean
244 horizontal climate velocity was 2.98 km yr^{-1} (Table 1), corresponding to an average displacement of
245 74.5 km over the next 25 years, although values ranged from zero to peaks of 120 km yr^{-1} , particularly
246 in the upper 30 m. Despite only 3.1% of points lacking future analogue, areas classified as ‘no change’
247 (both V_{xy} and $V_z = 0$) were scarce, representing just 11.9% of the Mediterranean. These rapid changes

248 suggest that many marine species will need to track suitable thermal habitats across considerable
249 distances within a few decades.

250

251 **[Table 1 here]**

252

253 Among all vertical biozones, the euphotic zone was the most exposed to climate-induced temperature
254 change, exhibiting the highest horizontal velocities and the most significant proportion of locations
255 without future analogues (Table 1). Mean horizontal velocity reached 4.31 km yr^{-1} , with maxima up
256 to $117.60 \text{ km yr}^{-1}$, primarily concentrated in areas close to the Strait of Gibraltar, along the Balearic
257 Sea coasts, the northern Aegean, and along the coasts of Tunisia and Libya (Figures 2-3). Moreover,
258 5.4% of locations lacked future analogues, forming pronounced clusters along the Tunisian coasts
259 and in the Gulf of Lions and the Northern Adriatic Sea. In contrast, areas of no change represented
260 11.3% of the euphotic zone and were predominantly found in the Eastern Mediterranean.

261

262 **[Figure 2 here]**

263 **[Figure 3 here]**

264

265 Deeper biozones across the Mediterranean Sea were generally more stable than the euphotic zone,
266 with mean horizontal velocities of 3.63 , 1.69 , and 2.49 km yr^{-1} , and no analogue proportions of 4.3%,
267 1.3%, and 3.9% in the mesophotic, mesopelagic, and bathyabyssopelagic biozones, respectively
268 (Table 1). Nonetheless, the bathyabyssopelagic biozone exhibited marked climate exposure in some
269 specific areas across the Mediterranean. We found widespread patches of elevated horizontal
270 velocities alongside persistent no analogue areas, with values exceeding 10.00 km yr^{-1} and up to 6.9%

271 no analogue (e.g., Ionian Sea; Figure 2). This indicates that even the deepest layers are not uniformly
272 stable and that climate-driven changes extend across the entire water column.

273 Finally, horizontal shifts toward future climate analogues showed no single dominant direction but
274 were predominantly aligned along the East-West and North-South axes rather than along oblique
275 directions. Each biozone exhibited distinct movement patterns, with no consistent direction emerging
276 at the basin scale (Figure 4). Comparing latitudinal and longitudinal components, shifts were
277 generally more pronounced along the North-South axis than the East-West axis. Across all depth
278 zones, northward and southward movements together accounted for approximately 40-50% of all
279 displacement directions, whereas East-West shifts typically accounted for 25-30%. Moreover, except
280 in the euphotic layer, where northward movement was slightly more frequent, southward shifts
281 dominated the latitudinal component in deeper biozones. Nonetheless, eastward movement remained
282 consistently represented across all depth ranges, contributing around 15-20% of total displacement
283 directions.

284

285 **[Figure 4 here]**

286

287 *3.2 Vertical component of climate velocity*

288 Most of the Mediterranean Sea experienced climate shifts in both horizontal and vertical directions.
289 Only 25.7% of points moved purely horizontally, whereas 45.8% underwent combined horizontal and
290 vertical displacement, and 13.4% shifted exclusively along the vertical axis. Across the water column,
291 mean vertical velocity was 1.77 m yr⁻¹ (Table 1), but this average masked extreme local values,
292 ranging from maxima of -70.00 m yr⁻¹ near 1000 m depth to 140.00 m yr⁻¹ at 4000 m. These results
293 highlight that vertical displacements are widespread, emphasising that climate-driven changes cannot
294 be fully captured by horizontal movement alone.

295 Vertical climate velocities displayed recurrently contrasting patterns across depth biozones. In the
296 euphotic zone, movement was predominantly downward, with a mean velocity $V_z = -0.19 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$,
297 although some areas, particularly the Levantine Sea, remained nearly stable (Figure 2). In the
298 intermediate biozones of the mesopelagic, vertical shifts were highly variable, with positive, negative,
299 and near-zero velocities frequently occurring in proximity. Upward-directed movement became more
300 common in the deeper layers of these zones, while localised downward shifts persisted, reaching
301 maxima around -40.00 m yr^{-1} (Figures 3). In the bathyabyssopelagic zone, vertical velocities were
302 generally strongly positive (mean $\approx 9 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$) and increased with depth, with the highest values
303 occurring in the Ionian Sea. Nevertheless, downward movement still occurred in the upper part of
304 this zone, with maxima below -50.00 m yr^{-1} . Overall, these patterns reveal that vertical displacement
305 is strongly depth-dependent and spatially heterogeneous, with opposing velocities often co-occurring
306 throughout the water column.

307

308 *3.3 Surface and bottom climate velocities and depth similarity*

309 At the surface, climate velocity values only partially reflected the dynamics observed across the full
310 water column (Figure S6). The mean horizontal velocity at surface level was lower than that in the
311 photic biozones ($V_{xy}=2.59 \text{ km yr}^{-1}$; Table 1), yet higher than in the pelagic zones, while the vertical
312 component showed strongly negative values ($V_z=-0.47 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$), indicating predominantly downward
313 movement. The spatial distribution of both components closely mirrored that of the euphotic zone.
314 However, horizontal velocities showed more widespread near-zero values, suggesting limited
315 horizontal displacement in several regions.

316 On the other hand, the seafloor appeared highly exposed to climate change, particularly in the shallow
317 and deep portions of the Mediterranean. The overall mean bottom climate velocity (5.66 km yr^{-1} ;
318 Table 1) exceeded that of any biozone, with pronounced peaks in the deepest areas such as the
319 southern Adriatic, Ionian Sea, and Strait of Sicily (Figure S6). In contrast, the western Mediterranean

320 and Levantine basins showed a larger proportion of cells with near-zero or moderate velocities (<5
321 km yr⁻¹). Locations without analogues were also relatively common (18.1%), occurring mainly along
322 the coasts, across the entire Adriatic, and in deep offshore sectors such as the central Tyrrhenian and
323 Ionian.

324 When examining depth similarity, horizontal and vertical velocities generally exhibited consistent
325 patterns within each biozone, except between 15 and 75 m and in the deepest layers (Figure 5). The
326 dissimilarity index for horizontal velocity remained low (≤ 0.2) across most depths, except in the
327 euphotic and mesophotic zones, where poor similarity (≈ 0.4) characterised the 15-75 m range.
328 Another marked discontinuity occurred in the bathyabyssopelagic zone, where layers between 2000
329 and 3000 m displayed distinct behaviours, differing substantially both among themselves and from
330 upper layers. Vertical velocity dissimilarities largely mirrored those of the horizontal component but
331 were generally less pronounced, except below 3000 m, where values exceeded 0.4, indicating
332 markedly different vertical velocities in the deepest layers. Overall, these results indicate that
333 similarity in climate velocity across depths is structured rather than uniform, with specific depth
334 ranges exhibiting distinct dynamics relative to adjacent layers.

335

336 **[Figure 5 here]**

337

338 *3.4 Basin-scale patterns*

339 Horizontal and vertical climate velocities differed markedly between the western and eastern
340 Mediterranean, with the eastern basins generally more heterogeneous and exposed to climate-driven
341 change than western basins.

342 Western basins (Provencal, Tyrrhenian, Alboran-Algerian, and Strait of Sicily) were generally more
343 stable, particularly below the euphotic zone (Figures S9, S12-S14). High horizontal velocities and

344 concentrations of no-analogue areas were mainly confined to coastal sectors in the euphotic and
345 mesophotic zones, while deeper biozones displayed mostly near-zero horizontal velocities (<2.00 km
346 yr^{-1} ; Table 2). Vertical velocities were generally modest, and a substantial proportion of points
347 showed null climate velocity. Across most basins, more than 6.1% of areas exhibited no change at all
348 depths, with this proportion increasing to 20-40% in deeper biozones. The Tyrrhenian was the main
349 exception, displaying consistently lower percentages across all depths. Downward-directed vertical
350 velocities persisted in deeper areas, particularly in the bathyabysopelagic Strait of Sicily and
351 Tyrrhenian (means below -4.1 m yr^{-1}), but concentration of negative means was also visible in the
352 Balearic Sea. The rest of the areas showed near-zero or upward-directed velocities, with the highest
353 peaks in the Ionian Sea at mesopelagic and bathyabysopelagic levels. Overall, these features indicate
354 that western basins are generally stable, with exposure restricted mainly to shallow coastal sectors.

355

356 **[Table 2 here]**

357

358 Eastern basins were more heterogeneous. The Levantine Sea was the most stable, exhibiting low
359 horizontal and vertical velocities throughout the water column and a higher proportion of no change
360 cells than points without analogues (Table 2; Figure S11). The Aegean exhibited contrasting patterns
361 between horizontal and vertical components: horizontal velocity was higher in the euphotic zone
362 (3.88 km yr^{-1}) and lower in deeper biozones (reaching 1.3 km yr^{-1} in the bathyabysopelagic),
363 whereas vertical velocity shifted from slightly negative at the surface to strongly positive in the
364 deepest layers (up to 10.2 m yr^{-1}). The Ionian Sea displayed a similar vertical trend, with negative
365 values in the upper water column and positive values in deeper layers, while horizontal velocity was
366 lower in intermediate zones but higher in the bathyabysopelagic (6.50 km yr^{-1}), accompanied by
367 clusters of no analogue points in these deeper layers (Figure S10).

368 Among all basins, the Adriatic was the most exposed, showing high horizontal velocities in the photic
369 zones (7.76 and 7.09 km yr⁻¹ for euphotic and mesophotic zones, respectively; Table 2), and
370 moderately lower values in pelagic zones (4.61 and 4.79 km yr⁻¹ for mesopelagic and
371 bathyabysso-pelagic, respectively). The vertical component was negative in the euphotic zone,
372 positive in the mesophotic zone, and strongly negative in the deepest zone. This basin also exhibited
373 the most significant proportion of no analogue points across the water column (up to 21.6% in the
374 euphotic; Figure S7), while no change cells remained present (around 29.0% in the
375 bathyabysso-pelagic).

376 Depth-dependent vertical shifts in climate conditions further highlighted regional differentiation.
377 Negative velocities dominated in the euphotic zone of nearly all basins, whereas positive velocities
378 became increasingly frequent in the mesophotic and mesopelagic zones, particularly in the Adriatic,
379 Aegean, and Ionian (Figure S7). In the deepest biozone, upward displacements were dominant in
380 some areas (Ionian), while other basins, such as the Tyrrhenian, Strait of Sicily, and Adriatic,
381 exhibited negative downward-directed velocities. These results reveal a complex interplay among
382 basin geography, depth, and climate exposure, with eastern basins exhibiting more heterogeneous and
383 pronounced vertical and horizontal shifts than western Mediterranean basins.

384

385 **4. DISCUSSION**

386 With this study we provide the first fully three-dimensional climate velocity assessment for the
387 Mediterranean Sea. Understanding how climate change reshapes marine habitats across depth is
388 essential for effective conservation; yet, most existing assessments rely solely on sea surface
389 temperature, overlooking the complex thermal dynamics of the water column, which are projected to
390 change under future climate scenarios (Adloff et al., 2015; Solidoro et al., 2022). By applying a fully
391 three-dimensional, analogue-based framework, we show that most present-day climatic conditions
392 are projected to shift in three dimensions. This reinforces growing evidence that horizontal climate

393 velocity alone provides an incomplete representation of marine climate change, as depth-dependent
394 responses play a critical role (Gruenburg et al., 2025). In our analysis, this three-dimensional
395 perspective revealed markedly different levels of climate change exposure across Mediterranean
396 biozones. While surface patterns are broadly similar across the region, deeper zones in the western
397 Mediterranean remain comparatively stable, whereas eastern basins exhibit higher velocities.
398 Importantly, such patterns cannot be understood using surface- or bottom-only climate velocity
399 approaches, which do not capture vertical climate patterns and implicitly assume a coherent response
400 across depths. These depth- and region-specific differences underscore the need for conservation
401 strategies tailored not only to individual basins but also to discrete depth ranges, ensuring the
402 protection of both shallow and deep-water refugia.

403 Our results revealed marked regional differentiation between the Western and Eastern Mediterranean,
404 reflecting the combined effects of basin geometry, circulation, and depth-dependent heat
405 redistribution in climate projections (Adloff et al., 2015). In the west, the euphotic zone experienced
406 substantial exposure, whereas deeper zones exhibited lower climate velocities, likely due to the
407 moderating influence of Atlantic inflow through the Strait of Gibraltar (Kubin et al., 2023; Schroeder
408 et al., 2016), consistent with projections showing reduced warming rates and more effective vertical
409 heat redistribution in western basins (Adloff et al., 2015). In contrast, the Eastern Mediterranean
410 showed more heterogeneous patterns: surface layers were generally less affected, but deeper regions
411 in the Ionian Sea displayed elevated velocities, confirming high climatic exposure of ecosystems at
412 these depths (Brito-Morales et al., 2020). The Levantine basin exhibited low exposure throughout the
413 water column, potentially reflecting long-standing warming trends and the profound environmental
414 transformations that have already occurred, and continue to occur, in this region (El-Geziry, 2021;
415 Pastor et al., 2020; Pisano et al., 2020). The Adriatic Sea had the highest velocities and the most
416 significant number of no analogue locations across all depths, confirming pronounced sensitivity to
417 climate-driven change. Limited water volume, restricted exchange with the broader Mediterranean,

418 and strong atmospheric forcing contribute to rapid warming and high temperature variability in this
419 shallow semi-enclosed basin (Da Costa et al., 2024; Moulin et al., 2024; Terzić et al., 2025). These
420 patterns highlight the importance of considering both physical oceanography and basin geography,
421 as well as depth-dependent processes, when evaluating climate exposure.

422 Focusing on the vertical dimension, our analysis revealed that the euphotic zone is the most exposed
423 biozone of the Mediterranean water column, exhibiting the highest climate velocities across the
424 region. This pattern aligns with projected warming trends: under RCP 8.5, surface waters are expected
425 to warm substantially more ($\sim 3\text{--}4^\circ\text{C}$ by year 2100) than deeper layers ($\sim 0.6\text{--}2^\circ\text{C}$; Parras-Berrocal et
426 al., 2023). This rapid warming can be explained by the fact that surface layers respond most directly
427 to atmospheric heat fluxes (Kubin et al., 2023), whereas subsurface and deep waters warm more
428 gradually due to their greater thermal inertia (Cheng et al., 2022). As a consequence, subsurface
429 waters remain comparatively cooler and more stable, helping explain why climate analogues for
430 euphotic conditions were predominantly found at greater depths. Across the Mediterranean, the mean
431 vertical climate velocity in the euphotic zone was consistently negative, indicating a dominant
432 downward-directed shift. In shallow coastal areas, where downward movement is physically
433 constrained by bathymetry (Jorda et al., 2019), we found distinct clusters of no analogue locations,
434 indicating the local loss of viable future conditions. Together, these results underscore the importance
435 of subsurface waters as potential vertical thermal refugia for surface-associated communities and
436 further highlight the need to explicitly consider depth when identifying conservation priority areas in
437 the Mediterranean Sea.

438 Our results indicated that the deepest portions of the Mediterranean Sea also represent potential
439 hotspots of climate-driven change, exhibiting high horizontal and vertical climate velocities. The deep
440 sea has traditionally been considered a thermally stable component of the water column, characterised
441 by cold temperatures that remain nearly constant over time (Danovaro et al., 2001; Levin & Le Bris,
442 2015), and therefore relatively less exposed to climate change than surface waters (Abraham et al.,

443 2013; Rogers, 2015). However, other modelling studies (Adloff et al., 2015; Reale et al., 2022;
444 Solidoro et al., 2022)– and our results – challenged this assumption, showing that the intrinsic thermal
445 stability of deep-sea environments may in fact increase their exposure to climate change: even modest
446 temperature increases, projected to reach up to $\sim 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ at abyssal depths by the end of the century
447 (Danovaro et al., 2017), can translate into substantial alterations of climatic conditions and induce
448 stress or shifts in the depth or latitudinal distribution of species (Brito-Morales et al., 2020; Danovaro
449 et al., 2001; Levin & Le Bris, 2015). Consistent with this interpretation, the high horizontal climate
450 velocities we observed in several deep Mediterranean regions, such as the Ionian Sea, the Strait of
451 Sicily, and the Southern Adriatic, can be explained by the fact that small warming rates, combined
452 with extremely weak horizontal temperature gradients, require large spatial displacements to locate
453 future climate analogues (Brito-Morales et al., 2020). These findings highlight that deep
454 Mediterranean environments are far from climatically inert and can experience substantial exposure
455 to climate change, reflecting the interaction of horizontal and vertical climate-driven displacement.

456 The direction of vertical climate velocity in deeper biozones varied markedly, with coexistence of
457 downward-, upward-, and null vertical velocities. This variability indicates that climate responses are
458 not transferable across depths, reinforcing the need to treat biozones as dynamically distinct
459 components of the climate system. Downward-directed vertical velocities primarily reflect the
460 pervasive temperature gradient of the ocean water column, where temperatures decrease with depth
461 (Lalli & Parsons, 1997), and are consistent with documented biological responses to upper-ocean
462 warming, as many species shift downward to track cooler thermal conditions (Chaikin et al., 2022;
463 Dulvy et al., 2008; Poloczanska et al., 2016). In the Western Mediterranean, this tendency may be
464 further reinforced by relatively colder intermediate waters associated with the Atlantic inflow through
465 the Strait of Gibraltar (Kubin et al., 2023). Null vertical velocities likely reflect recent changes in
466 water column stratification, whereby warming has produced a thick, relatively warm and
467 homogeneous deep layer, particularly in the Eastern Mediterranean (Artale et al., 2018), thus reducing

468 vertical thermal gradients and limiting the need for vertical displacement. More difficult to interpret
469 is the widespread occurrence of upward-directed vertical shifts, especially in pelagic zones below
470 1000 m. These may be linked to the progressive homogenisation of deep waters (Artale et al., 2018)
471 and to climate-induced density changes that promote the sinking of surface waters (Danovaro et al.,
472 2001), thereby accumulating warmer, saltier waters near the seabed. Such processes can locally
473 weaken or invert the vertical temperature gradient (Perry et al., 2005; Schroeder et al., 2016), causing
474 future climate analogues to be found at shallower depths. From a biological perspective, this
475 interpretation is supported by evidence that some taxa, depending on life-history traits, may respond
476 to climate change by shifting their distributions toward shallower and warmer waters (Chaikin et al.,
477 2022; Chaikin & Belmaker, 2023), a pattern also highlighted by biotic climate velocity analyses in
478 the Mediterranean showing upward depth shifts for some species (Sanz-Martín et al., 2024).

479 Within this vertically complex context, climate conditions at the surface most often found their closest
480 future analogues between 25 and 75 m depth, a range that broadly overlaps with the mesophotic zone
481 (30-150 m; Castellan et al., 2022). Mesophotic ecosystems are often considered potential climate
482 refugia due to their relative thermal buffering and reduced exposure to climatic and anthropogenic
483 stressors compared with surface ecosystems (Cerrano et al., 2019; Pichot et al., 2025; Silva-Montoya
484 et al., 2024). Our results, however, only partially support this hypothesis. Mesophotic depths
485 exhibited minimal vertical displacement and acted as a convergence zone for climate analogues
486 originating from both euphotic and deeper biozones, consistent with the concept of a vertical buffer
487 (Cerrano et al., 2019). At the same time, mesophotic layers experienced high climate velocities, a
488 substantial proportion of no analogue conditions, and a patchier warming trajectory than other depth
489 ranges, in line with evidence that climate change can be remarkably rapid and heterogeneous at these
490 depths (de la Maza et al., 2024). Thus, while mesophotic ecosystems may serve as transient refugia
491 for species shifting from adjacent layers, their resident communities appear highly exposed. This
492 challenges the assumption that mesophotic ecosystems function as consistent climate refugia (Pichot

493 et al., 2025; Silva-Montoya et al., 2024), instead highlighting their dual role as both buffers and
494 emerging hotspots of climatic instability.

495 Beyond vertical displacement, the horizontal component of climate velocity also exhibited
496 pronounced directional heterogeneity across the Mediterranean Sea. We observed multidirectional
497 shifts throughout the region and across most depth ranges. The euphotic zone represented the main
498 exception, showing a predominance of northward horizontal shifts, consistent with the expected
499 poleward displacement of mean sea surface temperatures under climate warming (Rhein et al., 2013).
500 In contrast, deeper biozones displayed no dominant horizontal direction, confirming increasing
501 multidirectionality with depth (Brito-Morales et al., 2020). However, when horizontal movements
502 were decomposed into latitudinal (north-south) and longitudinal (west-east) components, a
503 predominance of counter-poleward shifts emerged, with a slight tendency toward eastward
504 displacement. This pattern contrasts with prevailing expectations for the Mediterranean Sea, which
505 has been hypothesised to function as an ecological cul-de-sac (Ben Rais Lasram et al., 2010),
506 particularly in the north-western basins, where poleward temperature shifts (Rhein et al., 2013)
507 combined with the inflow of cooler Atlantic waters (Kubin et al., 2023) would favour northward-
508 westward climate tracking. Instead, our results suggested that suitable future climate conditions may
509 also be accessible through equatorward or eastward shifts. Perry et al. (2005) and Sanz-Martín et al.
510 (2024) showed that species can track their climatic niches by moving southward into deeper areas
511 with colder water masses. In this context, horizontal climate shifts appear closely linked to vertical
512 redistribution, highlighting the critical role of bathymetric structure and three-dimensional habitat
513 availability in shaping climate-driven movement and conservation priorities.

514 This study represents a first step toward integrating the vertical dimension into climate velocity
515 assessments for the Mediterranean Sea, with the specific aim of informing climate-smart conservation
516 planning. However, several methodological limitations should be acknowledged. First, our analysis
517 is based on a static comparison of present and future temperature conditions and therefore does not

518 explicitly account for ocean dynamics. Previous studies have shown that warming rates and heat
519 redistribution within the water column are strongly influenced by circulation, mixing, and convection
520 processes (Artale et al., 2018; Brito-Morales et al., 2020; Pisano et al., 2020), particularly in semi-
521 enclosed basins such as the Mediterranean Sea (Levin & Le Bris, 2015). Incorporating water-mass
522 dynamics into analogue-based climate velocity frameworks represents an important avenue for future
523 research and would likely improve the realism of projected climate-driven displacements.
524 Nevertheless, although approaches restricted to surface or bottom may be appropriate for specific
525 habitats or taxa, our results show that such simplified representations risk missing critical vertical
526 pathways of climate tracking and misidentifying potential refugia.

527 In addition, our approach allows climate analogues to be identified without explicitly considering
528 geographical or topographic barriers. As a result, horizontal climate velocities may be underestimated
529 in regions where realistic climate-tracking pathways would require detours around landmasses,
530 seamounts, or bathymetric features, rather than direct straight-line displacement. In such cases, the
531 effective distance required to track suitable climatic conditions may be substantially greater than that
532 implied by unconstrained climate velocity estimates.

533 A related but distinct limitation concerns ecological connectivity. High horizontal climate velocities
534 detected in isolated deep areas, such as the bathyabyssopelagic zones of the South Adriatic and the
535 Strait of Sicily, may reflect the availability of analogue climates in distant basins rather than locally
536 accessible refugia. This raises potential connectivity issues, as long-distance horizontal movements
537 implied by basin-wide analogue searches may exceed the dispersal capacity of many species (Brito-
538 Morales et al., 2018). Importantly, such basin-scale displacement suggests that future climate
539 conditions may no longer be represented locally, posing an additional challenge for marine
540 conservation planning. In these contexts, conservation efforts may need to move beyond identifying
541 climate refugia alone and also consider the emergence of climate bright spots (Queirós et al., 2021),

542 areas where future environmental conditions could become more suitable for some species despite
543 not representing climatic stability *sensu stricto*.

544 More broadly, climate velocity metrics implicitly assume unlimited dispersal and niche conservatism
545 (Brito-Morales et al., 2018), assumptions that are unlikely to hold universally across marine taxa.
546 Climate condition shifts do not necessarily translate into equivalent shifts in species distributions, as
547 behavioural, physiological, and evolutionary responses can strongly modulate climatic tracking
548 (Donelson et al., 2019). In particular, downward movements into deeper waters may be ecologically
549 constrained by bathymetry, habitat availability, food resources, light limitation, hydrostatic pressure,
550 oxygen minimum zones, and species-specific life-history traits (Chaikin et al., 2022; Jorda et al.,
551 2019). To address these limitations, we divided the water column into four ecologically meaningful
552 biozones, following the workflow proposed by Brito-Morales et al. (2020) and Doxa, Almpanidou,
553 et al. (2022). This approach helped limit unrealistic vertical jumps between environmentally
554 dissimilar depths and allowed us to incorporate key ecological constraints, such as light availability,
555 into the analogue search. At the same time, the framework is flexible and could be readily adapted to
556 species- or taxon-specific vertical distribution ranges, enabling future analyses to constrain climate-
557 analogue searches within ecologically realistic depth ranges tailored to particular organisms or
558 functional groups. In addition, restricting analogue searches within biozones reduced inflation effects
559 associated with uneven vertical spacing of temperature data, preventing shallow layers spaced by
560 only a few metres from being directly compared with deep layers separated by hundreds of metres.
561 Nevertheless, uneven depth resolution remains an inherent limitation of three-dimensional climate
562 analysis: larger vertical gaps in deeper zones may inflate estimates of vertical displacement, while
563 the absence of intermediate layers may obscure finer-scale climate-driven responses. This imbalance
564 in vertical sampling density may also influence dimensionality-reduction techniques, as the greater
565 number and higher variability of shallow layers could disproportionately shape the leading principal
566 component axes.

567 Finally, temperature is widely recognised as a primary driver of marine climate change and a key
568 determinant of ecological responses, underpinning many of the observed shifts in species
569 distributions, community structure, and ecosystem functioning (Parmesan, 2006; Soto-Navarro et al.,
570 2020; Wernberg et al., 2011). Accordingly, temperature-based climate velocity has proven to be a
571 powerful metric for capturing climate-driven change (García Molinos et al., 2016). However, climate
572 velocity is not inherently limited to temperature (Brito-Morales et al., 2018) and can be applied to
573 other core climate stressors, including pH, dissolved oxygen concentrations, and primary productivity
574 (Bopp et al., 2013). To date, most applications have focused on single-stressor climate velocity, an
575 approach that may overlook the multifaceted nature of climate change impacts on marine ecosystems
576 (Hu et al., 2024). Emerging work combining multiple variables, such as temperature and salinity
577 (Jonsson et al., 2018), highlights the potential of multivariate climate velocity frameworks to more
578 realistically represent future environmental change (Brito-Morales et al., 2018). Advancing toward a
579 multi-stressor perspective will therefore be essential for improving the identification of climate
580 refugia and strengthening the relevance of climate velocity metrics for conservation and sustainable
581 ocean management.

582 Overall, we demonstrated that integrating the vertical dimension fundamentally reshapes the
583 assessment of climate exposure and refugia in the Mediterranean Sea. By moving beyond surface-
584 only approaches, our three-dimensional analogue-based climate velocity framework revealed that
585 depth is not a uniform buffer against climate change, but a dynamic component where exposure and
586 stability vary markedly across basins and biozones. This perspective enables a more realistic
587 identification of climate refugia and exposure hotspots, providing critical insight for climate-smart
588 conservation and MSP. Incorporating depth-resolved climate dynamics into MSP can improve the
589 placement of conservation measures, anticipate limits to vertical and horizontal climate tracking and
590 support more resilient and forward-looking marine management in a rapidly changing Mediterranean.

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592

593 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION**

594 A.R., E.G., and S.M. conceptualized and designed the study and the methodology; A.R., S.M.
595 collected data, performed the analysis; E.G. supervised the study and secured funds; A.R. and E.G.
596 wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and A.R. designed the figures; all authors (A.R., E.G., S.M.,
597 D.C, and M.F.) contributed to the final version of the article.

598

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607 All scientific content, interpretations, and conclusions remain the sole responsibility of the authors.

608

609 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

610 The code supporting the findings of this study is publicly available on Zenodo at
611 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18340030>.

612 Raw input climate data are publicly available from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) and are
613 subject to the licensing and terms of use of the original data providers.

614

615 **DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST**

616 The authors declare no competing interests.

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945

946 **FIGURES**

947 **Figure 1:** Conceptual illustration of analogue-based climate velocity in two and three dimensions.

948 In both panels, the diagrams show present-day climate conditions (left grid) and future conditions (right
949 grid(s)), where a focal cell (green, with a species icon) represents a potentially stable climate for a species.

950 Arrows indicate the distance (d) the species would need to move to track its future climatic analogue.

951 (a) 2D analogue-based climate velocity. Future analogues are searched only along the horizontal X-Y plane,
952 so climate displacement is represented purely as a horizontal shift.

953 (b) 3D analogue-based climate velocity. The analogue search is extended to the vertical dimension (X-Y-Z),
954 allowing suitable conditions to occur at different depths and horizontal locations.

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958 **Figure 2:** Mean climate velocity (panel a) and analogue status (panel b) across Mediterranean biozones. (a)
 959 Horizontal (V_{xy} , km yr^{-1}) and vertical (V_z , m yr^{-1}) components of mean climate velocity for euphotic,
 960 mesophotic, mesopelagic, and bathyabyssopeagic zones. Horizontal velocities use a consistent colour scale
 961 across all biozones, from grey (near-zero) to yellow-blue (gradually higher), with no analogue points in purple.
 962 Vertical velocities use grey for near-zero, blue for downward, and red for upward movements, and purple for
 963 no analogue points; here, colour-scale limits vary by biozone to account for differing depth-layer spacing and
 964 to preserve fine vertical patterns. No analogue points are displayed only where more than half of the depth
 965 layers within a given biozone lack a future analogue. (b) Proportion of points at each depth with no analogue
 966 (i.e., points with no future climate analogue – in purple) and no change (i.e., points with null climate velocity:
 967 both V_{xy} and $V_z = 0$ – in grey).

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970 **Figure 3:** Depth profiles of horizontal and vertical climate velocity across Mediterranean biozones. For both
 971 horizontal (V_{xy} , panel a) and vertical (V_z , panel b) components, depth profiles are shown separately for mean
 972 velocities and maximum velocities across biozones. In the mean panels, the blue dots represent the average
 973 velocity at each depth, with the interquartile range depicted as a grey band bounded by dashed lines. In the
 974 maxima panels, red dots mark the highest velocity observed at each depth layer.

975

976 **Figure 4:** Vertical (panel a) and horizontal (panel b) directions of climate-driven movement across
 977 Mediterranean biozones.

978 (a) Mean vertical shifts for each depth layer within the four biozones. Dots represent the average vertical
 979 displacement, coloured blue for downward, red for upward, and grey for no movement, with dot size indicating
 980 the proportion of contributing points (smaller dots = more no-analogue cells). Vertical shifts use a logarithmic
 981 scale to accommodate depth-dependent spacing.

982 (b) Rose diagrams of horizontal movement direction ($0^\circ = \text{North}$). Each sector shows the proportion of points
 983 moving toward that angle, with summary boxes reporting movement toward the four cardinal sectors, plus the
 984 fractions of no-analogue, null horizontal velocity, and vertical-only shift.

985

986 **Figure 5:** Depth-layer dissimilarity of climate velocity within biozones. Heatmaps show pairwise dissimilarity
 987 between depth layers for horizontal (V_{xy}) and vertical (V_z) velocity in each biozone. Values are normalised
 988 from 0 (identical, blue) to 1 (maximal dissimilarity, red), highlighting depth-dependent variation and
 989 heterogeneity in climate-driven movement patterns across the Mediterranean water column.

990

991 **TABLES**

992 **Table 1:** Climate velocity metrics across Mediterranean depth domains. The table reports the mean horizontal
 993 (V_{xy} , km yr⁻¹) and vertical (V_z , m yr⁻¹) climate velocities and their standard deviations, together with the
 994 percentage of cells lacking a future climatic analogue and the percentage showing no change. Values are
 995 reported for the full Mediterranean water column (3D analogue search), the surface layer (extracted from the
 996 3D analysis), and the four biozones (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, bathyabysopelagic), for which
 997 analogue searches were restricted to the corresponding depth ranges. Seafloor values were obtained from a
 998 bottom-constrained analogue search and represent horizontal (2D) climate velocity.

999

	V_{xy} (km/yr)	V_z (m/yr)	Area with no analogue (%)	Area with no change (%)
Mediterranean Sea	2.98 ± 7.54	1.78 ± 8.06	3.1	11.9
<i>Depth domains</i>				
Surface layer (0.5m depth)	2.59 ± 7.68	-0.48 ± 0.29	3.1	7.5
Euphotic zone	4.31 ± 10.01	-0.19 ± 0.29	5.8	8.7
Mesophotic zone	3.63 ± 8.25	0.34 ± 0.92	4.3	11.3
Mesopelagic zone	1.69 ± 4.11	2.89 ± 6.31	1.3	15.4
Bathyabysopelagic zone	2.49 ± 4.39	9.07 ± 22.26	3.9	22.4
Seafloor	5.66 ± 9.57 (km/yr)		18.1	16.4

1000

1001 **Table 2:** Climate velocity metrics by Mediterranean basin and biozone. For each basin (Alboran-Algerian,
1002 Provençal, Sicily Strait, Tyrrhenian, Adriatic, Aegean, Ionian, Levantine), the table reports mean horizontal
1003 (V_{xy} , km yr⁻¹) and vertical (V_z , m yr⁻¹) climate velocities with associated standard deviations, together with
1004 the percentage of cells classified as no analogue or showing no change. Metrics are reported separately for the
1005 four biozones (euphotic, mesophotic, mesopelagic, bathyabyssopeagic).

1006

	<i>Western Mediterranean</i>				<i>Eastern Mediterranean</i>			
	Alboran-Algerian	Provençal	Sicily Strait	Tyrrhenian	Adriatic	Aegean	Ionian	Levantine
EUPHOTIC ZONE								
V_{xy} (km/yr)	6.66 ± 12.41	4.01 ± 7.6	4.52 ± 9.25	3.07 ± 6.65	7.76 ± 10.57	3.88 ± 10.89	3.02 ± 7.22	2.72 ± 7.64
V_z (m/yr)	-0.24 ± 0.3	-0.22 ± 0.28	-0.23 ± 0.32	-0.23 ± 0.26	-0.22 ± 0.28	-0.13 ± 0.28	-0.25 ± 0.31	-0.03 ± 0.2
area with no analogue (%)	23.8	2.2	6.5	1.9	4.5	8.8	6.3	2.7
area with no change (%)	1.5	18.1	2.0	3.3	21.6	3.9	5.0	9.5
MESOPHOTIC ZONE								
V_{xy} (km/yr)	4.2 ± 9.62	2.14 ± 6.05	2.65 ± 7.38	1.38 ± 4.59	7.09 ± 10.79	3.68 ± 8.86	3.8 ± 6.73	3.8 ± 8.12
V_z (m/yr)	0.35 ± 0.87	0.2 ± 0.78	0.18 ± 0.87	0.29 ± 0.88	0.3 ± 1.16	0.36 ± 0.91	0.47 ± 0.96	0.35 ± 0.95
area with no analogue (%)	11.2	3.1	6.2	2.5	5.1	4.9	2.9	2.1
area with no change (%)	6.8	9.4	7.2	6.1	6.5	28.7	15.1	23.0
MESOPELAGIC ZONE								
V_{xy} (km/yr)	0.63 ± 2.72	0.23 ± 1.25	1.61 ± 4.95	0.61 ± 2.44	4.61 ± 6.71	1.52 ± 4.62	2.86 ± 3.85	1.89 ± 4.89
V_z (m/yr)	1.8 ± 7.61	0.51 ± 6.89	2.28 ± 6.75	0.81 ± 6.38	3.92 ± 6.57	2.76 ± 4.46	6.38 ± 6.74	0.73 ± 2.95
area with no analogue (%)	2.7	2.5	1.6	0.6	1.4	0.3	2.5	0.2
area with no change (%)	13.1	6.4	22.5	1.5	13.6	43.7	14.7	27.3
BATHYABYSOPELAGIC ZONE								
V_{xy} (km/yr)	0.29 ± 0.87	0.16 ± 0.66	2.02 ± 7.59	0.58 ± 1.57	4.79 ± 8.45	1.13 ± 2.07	6.49 ± 4.96	0.92 ± 2.47
V_z (m/yr)	1.72 ± 13.51	4.33 ± 12.21	-4.13 ± 12.88	-5.31 ± 14.09	-5.19 ± 12.9	10.15 ± 16.34	24.96 ± 27.98	0.21 ± 12.73
area with no analogue (%)	10.6	2.1	0.2	8.2	2.2	0.2	6.9	4.9
area with no change (%)	32.1	9.4	42.8	0.5	29.0	49.5	16.3	31.5

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